

SEA THE VALUE

MARINE BIODIVERSITY BENEFITS
FOR A SUSTAINABLE SOCIETY

Supporting nature recovery by advancing natural
capital practices and developing essential
finance mechanisms

Final report of the Sea The Value project

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Target audience

The report is aimed at policy makers, arms-length bodies, marine researchers of all disciplines, economists and stakeholders of coastal areas, as well as buyers of credits from nature restoration.

Foreword

Aiming to be accessible and informative to a broad audience, this report details the key outcomes of “Sea the Value”, a 3-year transdisciplinary project. The aim of “Sea the Value” was to transform the application of economics, moving from the historical norm of economic growth driving environmental decline, to a situation where economic understanding is applied to better protect biodiversity and the multitude of benefits which it provides.

Global biodiversity continues to decline steeply, with WWF recently reporting that monitored wildlife populations have plummeted by 73% since 1970. This loss drives the destabilisation of ecosystems, resulting in a systematic risk to our health, food and water supply, but also to our economies and national security. To shift this trajectory, biodiversity must be placed at the core of our public and private decision making, with financial mechanisms playing a crucial role in this transition. Whilst this aspiration is widely shared, it is rarely achieved. Barriers to change include a limited understanding of how biodiversity provides benefits, low confidence in values associated with biodiversity, poor definition of who the beneficiaries of biodiversity are, and uncertainty regarding green investment routes. This work addresses each of these barriers aspiring to clear a path forward.

The multi-faceted interdisciplinary approach brought together disciplines of ecological and environmental economics, ecology, geography, governance and finance, drawing expertise from consultancies and academia, and working closely with the Coastal Partnership Network and the local communities of the Moray Firth and Solent. The outstanding team overcame the barriers and frustrations of interdisciplinary collaboration with patience, tenacity, and humour. The drive was to co-develop our approaches and outputs to be practically applicable and most importantly useful. A dedicated Programme Steering Group, including representation from government, industry and commerce, kept us on track and for these contributions the team was consistently grateful.

I hope this report provides valuable insights and sparks further exploration in this field. The finance mechanisms shared here combine cutting edge science and economics with an understanding of the needs of communities, partnerships, investors, landowners and government groups who may wish to apply them. A key message from this work is that through collaboration across disciplines and sectors there is hope that previous barriers may be overcome, and true potential and appetite for a future of biodiversity recovery.

By Prof Nicola Beaumont, Project Principal Investigator

Executive summary

This report summarises the findings of the Sea The Value project, carried out from 2022 to 2025. The project was led by Plymouth Marine Laboratory and research was carried out collaboratively among these research partners: eftec, University of Portsmouth, Daryl Burdon Ltd, University of Aberdeen, Coastal Partnership Network, Moray Firth Coastal Partnership.

The project vision was: 'To determine novel and policy relevant pluralistic values for marine biodiversity and apply these values to co-develop green investment options, leading to a transformative shift in our understanding and utilisation of the economics of biodiversity'.

The main objectives were to:

- Quantify the interlinkages between marine biodiversity, natural capital and ecosystem services, taking quantity (extent), quality (condition) and resilience into consideration.
- Determine the economic and social values associated with carbon sequestration and bioremediation of waste and apply these values to support natural capital accounting frameworks and engage real world communities in mapping social values and trade-offs.
- Connect the ecological, economic and social values of biodiversity to decision making through co-design and implementation of green investment to maintain and enhance biodiversity.

The work was split into eight distinct and interlinking steps which will each be explained in the following sections. The approach that we took allowed each team member to use their disciplinary tools to collect, assess and then pass on the data and information to address the aims of the project. The aim of this report is to showcase to readers how a natural capital assessment can be carried out and how we can use this approach to improve our understanding of the economics of biodiversity to such an extent that we can create outputs that can be used in decision making around natural capital and creating a financial market for ecosystem services.

The work was carried out in two different case study sites in the UK, the Cromarty Firth in Scotland and the Solent in England. They contrasted by the amount of ecological data available (more data in the Solent which is well researched, with some team members working on the Solent regularly) and by the establishment of stakeholder networks (the Cromarty stakeholders are well connected and keen to engage in research while Solent stakeholders are exposed to several projects leading to potential stakeholder fatigue and less engagement).

We hope the report can also guide readers in taking similar approaches in the coastal areas that they are involved in, either as users or managers in any sense. Therefore, each step also states the disciplines that worked on the step as well as the key skills needed to carry out the work. In this way it is easier to identify potential collaborators.

This report also signposts our key findings such as publications and training materials created during a training course provided to the Coastal Partnership Network.

Five key outcomes of the project

Deepening understanding of how biodiversity provides benefits

An asset-risk natural capital approach was applied at two case study sites, the well-studied Solent and data poor Cromarty Firth.

Fieldwork in the Solent filled gaps on how habitat quality and biodiversity shape ecosystem services provided by seagrass, saltmarsh, mudflats and oysters.

Engaging Communities in Pioneering Participatory Approaches

Coastal communities were actively involved in generating maps that link natural features, benefits, and beneficiaries. This process improved community access to, and understanding of, their local environment.

The Cromarty maps have been made freely available, and actively shared with schools, councils and a museum in Cromarty, and have supported local decisions on planning and restoration activities.

Valuing benefits of biodiversity and applying finance mechanisms

The diversity and dynamic qualities of the marine environment were reflected in the monetary valuation of ecosystem services. This provided a better understanding of uncertainties, and improved valuation data for economic appraisal, policy-developments, natural capital accounting, and green investment options.

Monetary values were integrated with ecosystem restoration science and beneficiary information (from the participatory research) to contextualise potential financial mechanisms to support marine habitat restoration.

Interdisciplinary collaboration resulting in enriched data, improved methods and impactful outputs

The project fostered deep interdisciplinary connections within the team and with project partners including government, NGOs and industry.

Training Coastal Partnerships in Natural Capital Approaches

Through four workshops the team shared expertise, empowering 24 coastal managers with practical skills.

Introduction

Biodiversity is still only sporadically integrated into public and private decision making (Tinch et al., 2019, Mckinley et al., 2019) despite significant scientific developments that have improved our understanding of how economies are embedded in nature and how biodiversity can be integrated into economic decision-making (Dasgupta, 2021, Bateman and Mace, 2020). The result is continuing biodiversity loss with negative implications for our society, economy, and wellbeing. Three key barriers to change include (1) a nascent understanding of how biodiversity provides benefits to society, resulting in a lack of applicable ecological data; (2) hesitance to apply social and economic values due to low confidence in the data and negligible beneficiary definition; and (3) high uncertainty regarding green investment routes (Luisetti et al., 2014, Börger et al., 2014). These challenges are particularly notable in the marine environment (Hooper et al., 2019, Committee, 2015).

Biodiversity is not easily defined and measured because it includes the wide variety of life, from bacteria to whales, and includes intraspecific (within species) and interspecific (among species) diversity. The term Natural Capital is defined as “the part of nature which directly or indirectly underpins value to people, including ecosystems, species, freshwater, soils, minerals, the air and oceans, as well as natural processes and functions” (Committee, 2019). Natural Capital Accounts (NCA) are a process to record natural capital “stocks”, and the flows of benefits they provide to society. Habitat and species data is a key part of the measurement of stocks of natural capital, making NCA a means to embed biodiversity into decision making. The UK Office of National Statistics (ONS) have been developing NCA to estimate the wealth of the UK’s environment (ONS, 2021). The UK marine assets are recorded at a value of £211 billion, with carbon sequestration and bioremediation found to be both highly valuable but also uncertain.

Yet, for new, green investment initiatives to be successful, investors and policymakers must trust that the NCA data is robust and fit for purpose. Critical evidence gaps persist in both, natural and economic sciences, and there is also a lack of integration of natural and economic sciences approaches and data. A critical evidence gap in natural sciences relates to data on the condition of ecosystems and of their resilience to pressures. But such data is needed to understand how ecosystems provide us with services such as nutrient and carbon removal (Oliver et al., 2015). For example, despite efforts to measure nitrogen (N), phosphorous (P) and carbon (C) sequestration and storage (Kellogg et al., 2014, Burrows et al., 2014), significant variability exists in long term storage estimates (Krause-Jensen and Duarte, 2016, Beaumont et al., 2014). Excluding condition and resilience creates significant risks for green investment into ecosystem restoration, and also impacts scalability for national accounting (Watson et al., 2020, Grizzetti et al., 2019).

In addition, valuing such regulating services is challenging as they are not traded in markets, so their valuation relies on static or outdated valuation approaches. Different types of monetary value can cause confusion, e.g. national accounting is primarily concerned with measuring economic activity, while local communities focus on changes in welfare. These purposes call for different measures of value, with the key distinction between data that reflect economic transactions (‘exchange values’) and data that reflect all benefits to people (‘welfare values’). The different value types are complementary, but not interchangeable, which can cause confusion resulting in misinterpretation and poor application of monetary values.

To uncover the diverse value sets, mixed methods approaches are recommended. Participatory mapping is a novel stakeholder-driven approach enabling community engagement through face-to-face workshops (Burdon et al., 2022) co-producing knowledge and facilitating spatial mapping of biodiversity, ecosystem features, values, benefits and beneficiaries (Damastuti and de Groot, 2019). From a management and investment perspective, the outputs can help identify which benefits and beneficiaries may be impacted by an intervention, and what direction that impact may take.

The aim of this project was to link marine ecological understanding of coastal habitats with social science approaches and green finance mechanisms to support nature restoration. Key coastal habitats assessed were seagrass beds, oyster beds, saltmarshes and mud. These habitats were chosen because the former three have high potential for restoration through human intervention while the latter is the most widespread and a useful control habitat. The focus was on the role which marine biodiversity plays in providing climate regulation and nutrient bioremediation services. Climate regulation is defined as 'Regulation of temperature and humidity, including ventilation and transpiration' (Haines-Young and Potschin, 2018) however we focus on the aspect of carbon sequestration and storage. Bioremediation of waste is defined as 'Regulation of the chemical condition of waters by living processes' (Haines-Young and Potschin, 2018), and we focussed on the aspects related to the nutrients nitrogen (N) and derivatives of phosphorus (P) (herein referred to as Bioremediation).

This report shows the Sea The Value approach to addressing the research gaps explained above. It also aims to inspire readers to carry out such research in their area or to better understand how decisions around green finance mechanisms of restoration can be made.

Two case study sites

Two distinct case study sites were chosen for this study (Figure 1). Our intention was to choose two sites with different levels of ecological knowledge attached to them. We therefore looked for a case study site with long-term and intense data collection and also ongoing restoration efforts and another where not much was known about the ecology and little active research being carried out. While the Solent European Marine Site is well studied with cutting-edge restoration research taking place in addition to other ongoing marine natural science and monitoring, this is less so for the Cromarty Firth where research and monitoring are taking place only sporadically.

Figure 1: Location of the Cromarty Firth (Scotland) and the Solent (England) case study sites.

Solent

The Solent is a large, semi-enclosed water body between the Isle of Wight and the south coast of England (Figure 1). This water body is a busy public waterway with Portsmouth harbour acting as one of the UK's largest naval docks and Southampton water one of the most active ports in the world. The area is of ecological importance; internationally designated with seagrass meadows, saltmarsh, native oysters and intertidal mudflats. It is bordered by and forms part of several nationally important protected landscapes (Foster et al., 2014). The Solent Strait is bordered by agricultural land and urban areas with wastewater treatment plants, with consequent adverse impacts on marine water quality. For example, between 2022 and 2024, 100,000 hours of storm overflow discharges into the Solent and its catchment rivers have been recorded (ABPmer, 2024).

The focus here is on Langstone and Chichester Harbours on the South Coast of England, within the wider Solent catchment. The two harbours have suffered significant declines in key habitats over many decades, but at the same time host some of the most protected areas of coast in the UK. Although the drivers of these declines are numerous, the

cumulative effects have resulted in considerable losses of key habitats such as saltmarsh and seagrasses with concomitant reductions in quality for those areas that currently remain.

The inclusion of the two harbours in the Sea the Value Project as case studies is because they are exemplars of a highly impacted coastal eutrophic system in UK waters, but more importantly have a considerable body of data on: key water parameters, habitat extent and condition and some of the services provided by the dominant ecosystems. These baseline data were a critical building block for the Sea Value Project to determine the pluralistic values for marine biodiversity to the diverse stakeholders and users of the harbours, thus enabling the Sea the Value Project team to include extent and quality into natural capital valuations that will feed into policy.

Cromarty Firth

The Cromarty Firth is located on the north-east coast of Scotland (Figure 1). It extends for 25 km from the mouth of the River Conon at Conon Bridge into the wider Moray Firth. It is a large estuary made up of a deep-water channel surrounded by temperate estuarine habitats including intertidal mudflats and sandflats, saltmarsh, wet grassland, seagrass, blue mussels and horse mussels.

In 1969, it was designated as a national Site of Special Scientific Interest for its intertidal sand and mudflats, saltmarsh habitats and for its nationally important populations of wintering birds. In 1999, it was further designated as a European Special Protection Area. The deepwater channel has supported the region's shipping industry, with active harbours present at Cromarty and Invergordon, which are managed by the Cromarty Firth Port Authority. The Cromarty Firth was recently awarded Green Freeport status as part of the wider Inverness and Cromarty Firth Green Freeport and as such will maximise local and Scotland-wide benefits from renewable energy projects placing the Highlands at the heart of the drive towards net-zero.

In terms of data availability, the body of knowledge around Cromarty Firth ecology and environmental conditions is relatively poor compared to the case study site in the Solent. The RSPB created new habitat through managed realignment in Nigg Bay in 2008 and monitoring has been done through Royal Society for the Protection of Birds (RSPB) for several years after this process was finished.

Other data is provided through statutory monitoring initiatives such as the Water Framework Directive.

The Sea the Value approach

To achieve the project vision, eight interlinked and iterative steps were undertaken (Figure 2). The final step was used to apply all findings to scenarios that can allow realistic discussions around creating a green investment model into nature restoration. Data created in earlier steps was used to create diverse value assessments and for economic investment modelling.

Figure 2: Flowchart of approach, each step is described in the following pages

Step 1 Develop asset and risk registers at case study sites

Key skills required: Marine ecologists, GIS skills, desk-based research

Step 1 provided the baseline data for most other parts of the project. Two asset and risk registers were developed one for each case study site. An asset register is “an inventory of the natural assets in an area and their condition” and useful to identify all the benefits that come from nature (Committee, 2017). The register is created in both tabular and map form.

Figure 3: Flowchart of approach in Step 1

All maps were created using ARCGIS Pro.

For the asset register (Figure 3), the focus was on habitat extent data, specifically for seagrass, oysters, saltmarsh and soft sediments. At the same time, condition data were collected where it was available. Condition data were mostly derived from Water Framework Directive reports.

Habitat data was sought from several sources to ensure that the entire basin of each case study site could be accounted for. For the Cromarty (Figure 4), the majority of habitat information came from Nature Scot reports and had been created between 2010 and 2016.

Data for the Solent case study site (Figure 4) was taken from JNCC and from Watson et al. (2020).

a

Natural Capital Stocks Baseline map - Chichester & Langstone Harbours

b

Natural Capital Stocks Baseline Map - Cromarty Firth

Figure 4: Natural capital stocks in the Solent (a) and the Cromarty (b)

The input for the risk register was based on information found on activities carried out in both case study sites, such as bait collection, mooring, fishing and harbour maintenance. The activities were mapped where they occur (Figure 5).

a

Activities and pressures map - Chichester and Langstone Harbours

b

Natural Capital Stocks Baseline Map - Cromarty Firth

Figure 5: Activity and pressure data maps for Solent (a) and Cromarty (b)

Each activity was linked to the pressures it creates on the marine habitat using the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (JNCC) Pressures Activities Database (JNCC, 2022). To

measure the potential effect of pressures on the habitats, the MarESA Sensitivity matrix (Tyler-Walters, 2023) was linked to the previous two datasets. This provided information on the likely condition and vulnerability of the affected habitats to the pressures. Finally, habitat extent was used to create an ecosystem service matrix which finally gave the asset and risk registers which could then be used in later stages of the project (Steps 6,7 and 8). Activity and risk maps were also created in ARCGIS Pro.

Figure 6: An example risk map overlaying mudflat (brown) and saltmarsh areas (green) in the Solent with bait digging/harvesting. Hatched: harvesting on salt marsh, dotted: harvesting on mud flat.

All the information thus gathered was used to assess the extent of habitat affected by activities (Table 1) and how this may impact the condition of each habitat (Table 2). The resulting map for the Solent is given as an example (Figure 6).

Table 1: Example of a calculation of exposure of each area to pressures and resulting likely habitat condition (Solent only)

Habitat	Area of habitat (ha)		Powerboating launch and recovery	Vessel anchoring	Anchoring exposed (25% of area)	Vessel mooring	Max mooring density	Max abrasion (m ₂)	Max abrasion (ha)	Abrasion (%)	Extent Loss (m ₂)	Extent loss (ha)	Physical loss (%)
	Harvesting	Area											
A2.11 Shingle (pebble) and gravel shores	78.85	1.54	6.69	3.29	0.82	0.79	0.72	202.80	0.02	0.03	1.72	<0.005	<0.005
A2.3 Littoral mud	3708.20	166.68	65.00	79.75	19.94	99.22	90.29	25601.01	2.56	0.07	216.71	0.02	<0.005
A2.5 Saltmarsh	368.99	14.68	5.28	10.22	2.56	11.31	10.29	2917.35	0.29	0.08	24.69	<0.005	<0.005
A3.2 Moderate energy infralittoral rock	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	<0.005	<0.005

Habitat	Area of habitat (ha)		Harvesting		Powerboating launch and recovery		Vessel anchoring		Anchoring exposed (25% of area)		Vessel mooring		Max mooring density	Max abrasion (m ₂)	Max abrasion (ha)	Abrasion (%)	Extent Loss (m ₂)	Extent loss (ha)	Physical loss (%)
A5.1 Sublittoral coarse sediment	221.05		0.00	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00		13.41	12.21	3460.98	0.35	0.16	29.30	<0.005	<0.005
A5.2 Sublittoral sands and muddy sands	31134.19		0.69	0.00		2.14		58.65		14.66		3.77	3.43	971.42	0.10	0.00	8.22	<0.005	<0.005
A5.3 Sublittoral cohesive mud and sandy mud communities	603.97		7.42	1.23		37.87		76.89		19.22		200.51	182.46	51733.27	5.17	0.86	437.91	0.04	0.01
A5.4 Sublittoral mixed sediment			0.00			0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	<0.005	<0.005
A5.435 Ostrea edulis beds on shallow sublittoral muddy mixed sediment	1151.24		0.00	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	<0.005	<0.005
A5.34 Infralittoral fine mud	0.00		0.00			0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	<0.005	<0.005

Habitat	Area of habitat (ha)		Powerboating launch and recovery	Vessel anchoring	Anchoring exposed (25% of area)		Vessel mooring	Max mooring density	Max abrasion (m ₂)	Max abrasion (ha)	Abrasion (%)	Extent Loss (m ₂)	Extent loss (ha)	Physical loss (%)
	Harvesting													
A5.52 Kelp and seaweed communities on sublittoral sediment	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	<0.005	<0.005
A5.53 Sublittoral seagrass beds	278.86	0.57	0.21	0.00	0.16	0.04	3.21	2.92	826.93	0.08	0.03	7.00	<0.005	<0.005

Table 2: Likely habitat condition calculated from Table 1

Habitat	Likely Condition Area %				
	Good	Fair	Degraded	Poor	Very Poor
A2.11 Shingle (pebble) and gravel shores	98	0	0	2	<0.01
A2.3 Littoral mud	96	0	0	4	<0.01
A2.5 Saltmarsh	94	0		2	4
A3.2 Moderate energy infralittoral rock	100		0	0	0
A5.1 Sublittoral coarse sediment	100				<0.001
A5.2 Sublittoral sands and muddy sands	100	<0.1			<0.001
A5.3 Sublittoral cohesive mud and sandy mud communities	100	0	0	0	0
A5.4 Sublittoral mixed sediment	100				
A5.435 <i>Ostrea edulis</i> beds on shallow sublittoral muddy mixed sediment	100	0	0	0	0
A5.34 Infralittoral fine mud	100	0	0	0	0
A5.52 Kelp and seaweed communities on sublittoral sediment	100	0	0	0	0
A5.53 Sublittoral seagrass beds	99.75				0.25

1. Link to JNCC Pressure Activities Database: [Marine Pressures-Activities Database \(PAD\) v1.5 | JNCC Resource Hub](#)
2. Link to MARESA: [Marine Evidence based Sensitivity Assessment \(MarESA\) - summary - MarLIN - The Marine Life Information Network](#)

Step 2 Participatory mapping for diverse social values and beneficiaries

Key skills required: Social sciences, stakeholder engagement, workshop facilitation, participatory mapping, GIS, scientific reporting.

Participatory mapping is a stakeholder-driven approach which aims to capture local knowledge and empower place-based discussions around socio-cultural values. A series of three participatory mapping workshops were undertaken in collaboration with coastal partnerships and communities in the Cromarty Firth and the Solent with the same structure, methodology and scenarios applied at both sites. Workshop 1 is included within Step 2,

whereas Workshops 2 and 3 are discussed in Step 4. Step 1 (asset/risk register development) was not necessary to carry out Step 2, a research paper will explore the commonalities and differences between stakeholder produced maps and maps created in Step 1.

Features Mapping

The first workshop was used to identify the relationships between the natural (capital) features and the benefits which these features provide for society. Once a list of features had been produced by the workshop attendees, the features were then drawn on to A1 satellite images of the case study sites with attendees developing their own key for features. Due to the size of the case study sites, multiple maps were created in each location (e.g. inner, middle and outer Cromarty Firth), and numbers of attendees were restricted (21 maximum) to allow each participant to actively contribute to the mapping exercises. Discussions around the types of features, their location, condition and extent were captured by the facilitators. The paper map outputs were mapped within ArcGIS software, with the maps from the different group being combined into a single map per case study site before being reviewed and refined by the workshop attendees. Final outputs from the features maps are presented in Figure 7 for the Cromarty Firth, and Figure 8 for the Solent. All digital maps were distributed to workshop participants, and in addition, printed maps were distributed to local schools and libraries in the Cromarty Firth where, for example, they have been displayed in local exhibitions on the natural environment.

Figure 7: Stakeholder features maps from the Cromarty.

Figure 8: Stakeholder features maps from the Solent.

Benefits Mapping

Once the features were mapped, attendees were asked to compile a list of 'benefits' which they receive from their local marine environment. No definition of benefits was provided, and attendees were told to think about benefits in the broadest sense. Once a list of benefits was compiled, attendees were asked to map these onto the features. For example, if they identified recreational boating as a benefit, then this would be assigned to the water channel where the benefit is materialised, or if they identified carbon sequestration as a benefit then this benefit was assigned to all features which the attendees believed delivered this benefit (e.g. saltmarsh, seagrass). Where it was deemed by the stakeholders that a benefit was

provided by all features, then these were listed at the bottom of the map. Discussions around the types of benefits and their linkages with features were captured by the facilitators. This resulted in matrices of natural features versus benefits for both the Cromarty Firth (Figure 9) and Solent (Figure 10).

Natural Features	Societal Benefits (SB)											Abiotic Benefits (AB)				Economic Benefits (EB)			Other Benefits (OB)		
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
	SB1	SB6	SB7	SB8	SB9	SB10	SB11	SB12	SB13	SB14	SB15	AB1	AB2	AB3	AB4	EB1	EB2	EB3	OB1	OB2	OB3
	Food (wild, farmed) / Drink	Healthy climate (Carbon Sequestration)	Prevention of coastal erosion	Sea defence	Waste burial / removal / neutralisation	Tourism / Nature Watching	Spiritual and cultural well-being	Aesthetic benefits	Education, research	Physical health benefits	Psychological health benefits	Wind energy	Water resources (quality and quantity)	Archaeology / Geology / Geomorphology	Transport	Place to live	Place to work	Industry	Habitat / species biodiversity	Intrinsic value	Functioning ecosystems
Beach		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X			X	X	X	X	X
Seagrasses	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X		X			X			X	X	X
Mudflats	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X			X	X	X	X	X
Saltmarshes	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X			X	X	X	X	X
Blue mussels	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X		X		X	X			X	X	X	X	X
Sandbanks				X		X	X	X	X		X				X		X			X	X
Natural Firth channel	X	X				X	X		X	X	X		X		X		X	X	X	X	X
Dunglass Island						X	X	X	X	X	X			X			X	X		X	X
Burns						X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X			X			X	X
Woodland		X					X				X		X	X			X	X		X	
Old oyster beds							X		X										X	X	
Horsemussels		X			X		X		X				X							X	
Cliffs			X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X			X			X	X	X	X	
Brownfield						X	X		X					X		X			X	X	X

Figure 9: Natural features versus benefits matrices from the Cromarty Firth

	Societal Benefits (SB)												Abiotic (AB)		Economic Benefits (EB)			Other Benefits (OB)			
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
	SB1	SB5	SB6	SB7	SB8	SB9	SB10	SB11	SB12	SB13	SB14	SB15	AB2	AB4	EB1	EB2	EB3	OB1	OB2	OB4	OB5
Natural Features	Food (wild, farmed) / Drink	Medicines and blue biotechnology	Healthy climate (Carbon Sequestration)	Prevention of coastal erosion	Sea defence	Waste burial / removal / neutralisation	Tourism / Nature Watching	Spiritual and cultural well-being	Aesthetic benefits	Education, research	Physical health benefits	Psychological health benefits	Water resources (quality and quantity)	Transport	Place to live	Place to work	Industry	Habitat / species biodiversity	Intrinsic value	Connectivity	Sense of space
Saltmarsh	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Seagrass meadow/Zostera marina	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X
Sand dunes			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X					X	X	X		X
Sandbank/Sand spit (Billy Line)	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X					X	X	X		X
Saline lagoons			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X					X	X	X		X
Sandflats	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X		X
Shellfish beds/Shellfish dredge areas	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X
Mudflats	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Vegetated Shingle	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X		X	X	X	X
Gravel and shell beach			X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X		X	X	X	X
Sub tidal mixed sediments	X	X	X	X	X	X				X					X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Scrub	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X						X	X	X	X
Fresh water input			X	X				X	X	X		X	X					X	X	X	
Oysters	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Reed bed	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X			X	X	X	X
Algal cover	X	X	X		X	X	X	X		X	X	X				X	X	X	X		X
Woodland/Mixed Woodland/Ancient woodland	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Salt pans			X		X	X	X	X		X		X				X	X	X	X	X	X
Shingle banks			X	X	X	X		X	X	X		X				X		X	X	X	X
Kelp	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X
Invasive plant species (R. cugosa)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X				X	X	X	X	X	X
Clams/cockles (Hand gathered)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X
Shingle beach/Shingle and Sand/Shingle and Shell			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X					X	X	X	X	X

Figure 10: Natural features versus benefits matrices from the Solent

The methods and results were reported in workshop reports for each site (Anbleyth-Evans, 2023, Van Der Schatte Olivier, 2024), and formed the basis for training materials (Collar, 2025), conference presentations (Burdon, 2024, Burdon, 2025) and papers in preparation for publication (Burdon et al., submitted; Gormley et al., in prep.; Burdon et al., submitted).

Outputs:

3. Cromarty Firth: [Cromarty-Firth-Workshop-1-report.pdf](#)
4. Solent: [Solent-Workshop-1-Report.pdf](#)
5. Burdon, D., Pott, T., Van Der Schatte Olivier, A., Gormley, G., Anbleyth-Evans, J., Beaumont, N.J., Ndah, A., Paxton, V., Preston, J., Watson, G.J. & Watson, S.C.L., submitted 2025. Participatory mapping to support coastal communities to ‘Sea the Value’ of marine restoration initiatives. *submitted* to *Ecosystem Services*.
6. Gormley, K. et al. *in prep.* Is participatory mapping a cost-effective method to map estuarine and coastal habitats?
7. Burdon, D., Potts, T., Tillin, H., Watson, S.C.L & Anderson, L., submitted 2025. A Decade of the marine ecosystem service matrix approach: Review of applications, developments and future research. Submitted to *Ecosystem Services*, November 2025.

Step 3 Field data collection

Key skills required: marine ecologist, permit acquisition, understanding and carrying out sampling according to standard protocols, advanced ecological statistics. All fieldwork was carried out in the Solent. We assessed the habitat quality and biodiversity of four key intertidal and shallow subtidal ecosystems (saltmarshes, seagrass meadows, oyster beds, and mudflats) using several sampling sites (Figure 11), and the impact of these on nutrient remediation and carbon sequestration.

Figure 11: Location of sampling sites in Chichester and Langstone Harbours.

Figure 12: Low and high condition (as measured by plant density) for seagrass. Photo © Andrew van der Schatte Olivier

To identify areas of higher biodiversity, we utilised condition to define the sampling areas; split into high and low condition for seagrass (example Figure 12) and oysters, as well as adjacent unvegetated areas (mudflat) as a control. Large variation exists between the seagrass habitat found across the UK, demonstrating the plasticity of seagrass to respond to a wide range of environmental conditions (Bertelli et al., 2021). We focussed on a suite of parameters to assist in understanding condition including the following: habitat extent, shoot density/percentage cover, leaf length. We counted the number of shoots in a 0.1m² quadrat and then randomly selected blades to reflect canopy height using these and other morphometrics as a proxy for plant surface area.

Typically, saltmarsh condition is measured using the following indicators: overall extent, the presence of saltmarsh zones (e.g. Pioneer, *Spartina* spp. Mid-low, Upper Marsh, Reedbeds) and taxa diversity. At the saltmarsh sites, low, mid and high marsh areas were assessed for plant species biodiversity using quadrats.

OSPAR have defined “native oyster beds” as “*Ostrea edulis* occurring at densities of 5 or more per m² on shallow, mostly sheltered sediments (OSPAR, 2009). The Solent has seen declines in native oyster populations since the late 1800’s as a result of increased water pollution, habitat loss, overfishing, competition from invasive species, and disease (Thomas et al., 2022). Few native oysters can be found and then they are usually mixed with pacific oysters *Magallana (Crassostrea) gigas*. Therefore, we split areas into either low/high density *C. gigas* areas and areas with both species. Oysters within each quadrat were measured and weighed in addition to the assessment of other macrofauna present in the sediments beneath the oysters.

For all habitats across both harbours (each habitat also had an adjacent mudflat as a control site), sediment cores for macrofauna diversity and abundance, total organic content (as a proxy for carbon storage), pore water ammonia concentrations, and denitrification data were collected.

The methods and results will be reported in a series of scientific publications/reports focussing on the effects of habitat quality/diversity on carbon sequestration and storage. These may be specific to an individual habitat (e.g. seagrass) but will also compare habitats and the interaction of site condition too. Finally, the fieldwork from the Solent will be compared against available data for the Cromarty Firth and also put in the context of the other components of the Sea the Value project.

Outputs

8. *Fabra M., van der Schatte Oliver, A., Morrall, Z., Watson, G., Woods, F., *Preston, J. (2024). Nutrient cycling processes in remnant UK oyster habitat: Filtration rates, nutrient assimilation and deposition by *Ostrea edulis*, and denitrification rates mediated by remnant mixed oyster habitat. Report to The Environment Agency, England. Call off ref: RDE305, Version 0.1, March 2024. *Joint first authors.

Step 4 Diverse social values and beneficiaries

Key skills required: Stakeholder engagement, workshop facilitation, participatory mapping, GIS, scientific reporting.

Trade-off assessments using future scenarios (Workshops 2 and 3)

Active restoration can be implemented following the voluntary purchase of agricultural land (as described below for managed realignment in the Cromarty Firth) or using the drag box method. Trade-off assessments, based on future scenarios, allow us to identify and be transparent on the potential gains and losses under each of these methods and to identify which stakeholders may be impacted by such active restoration interventions.

Future restoration scenarios of managed realignment and native oyster restoration were explored in Workshop 2 at each location to investigate the potential impacts of such management interventions on the delivery of benefits and to identify potential beneficiaries who may be impacted (positively or negatively) under these future scenarios. Outputs from the matrix approach, which identifies the relative importance of natural features in delivering benefits, were used to assist the workshop attendees in undertaking trade-off assessments. Example outputs for the restoration of saltmarsh in the Cromarty Firth and Solent are provided in Figure 13 and Figure 14 respectively below.

Figure 13: Assessment of the impact of a hypothetical managed realignment future scenario on the benefits delivered by the Cromarty Firth. The shaded bars with black dot represent the combined change from the 'Business-as-usual' scenario (represented as 0), with the variance of responses across participant groups in the workshop represented by the dashed line. A question mark reflects where scores were unknown by one (?) or two (??) group.

Figure 14: Assessment of the impact of a hypothetical managed realignment future scenario on the benefits delivered by the Solent. The shaded bars with black dot represent the combined change from the 'Business-as-usual' scenario (represented as 0), with the variance of responses across the three stakeholder groups represented by the dashed line. A question mark reflects where scores were unknown by one group.

Logic Chain Development

Whilst examples of logic chains exist within the literature which link natural capital to benefits, the participatory mapping workshops developed these chains further by identifying the stakeholders, termed here as the 'beneficiaries', who are reliant or dependent on those benefits. Logic chains were produced linking the natural features and benefits (as identified in Step 2 above) and the beneficiaries who are reliant or dependent on these benefits. Beneficiaries were identified as those organisations who have attended previous 'Sea the Value' workshops or who have engaged in the project. We note that while this is a limited – but representative – group of stakeholders, the aim is not to map all beneficiaries in the region but rather to explore the in-depth relationships of a range of beneficiaries and demonstrate the value of the participatory approach. Such logic chains can be viewed through either a natural capital lens (read left to right) focusing on the importance of linkages from natural capital to people or a beneficiary lens (read right to left) focusing on the reliance or dependence of society on the benefits delivered by natural capital (Figure 15). Example logic chains for saltmarsh are provided below (Figure 16 and Figure 17).

Figure 15: Logic chain structure to be populated during the participatory mapping workshop series.

Figure 16: Natural capital logic chain focussing on saltmarsh restoration in the Cromarty Firth.

Figure 17: Natural capital logic chain focussing on saltmarsh restoration in the Solent.

The outputs from Step 2 and Step 4 have demonstrated that participatory mapping is a valuable method when developing restoration initiatives in the natural environment. It can be deployed prior to an intervention, as it empowers stakeholders to engage in natural capital discussions by developing a common language and provides insights into the respective reliance/dependence of individuals and organisations on benefits provided by the natural environment. This early work is critical in examining the common good that lies within natural capital assets, the potential trade-offs in decisions and developing a common reference point and language. It enables a strategic approach for restoration initiatives to occur, based upon dialogue, mutual understanding and local engagement.

Participatory mapping can also be used to help practitioners focus on areas with the highest restoration potential, and therefore improve resource allocation, and can provide visual evidence to secure conservation funding and inform policy decisions.

The methods and results were reported in two workshop reports for each site (Burdon et al., 2023; Burdon et al., 2024; Van der Schatte Olivier et al., 2024; Watson et al., 2024), and formed the basis for training materials (Collar, 2025), conference presentations (Burdon et al., 2024; 2025) and a number of papers in preparation for publication (Burdon et al., submitted; Gormley et al., in prep.; Burdon et al., submitted). Further details are provided below.

9. Burdon, D. & Potts, T., 2023. Cromarty Firth Workshop 2: Scenarios Assessments. Report produced for the NERC/ESRC-funded Sea the Value Project, December 2023. <https://pml.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Cromarty-Firth-Workshop-2-Report.pdf>
10. Burdon, D. & Potts, 2024. Cromarty Firth Workshop 3: Logic Chains. Report produced for the NERC/ESRC-funded Sea the Value Project, April 2024. <https://pml.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Cromarty-Firth-Workshop-3.pdf>
11. Van der Schatte Olivier, A., Watson, G., Preston, J., Watson, S.C.L. & Ndah, A., 2024. Solent Workshop 2. Scenarios Assessments. Report produced for the NERC/ESRC-funded Sea the Value Project, December 2023. <https://pml.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Solent-Workshop-2-Report.pdf>

12. Watson, G. Van Der Schatte Olivier, A., Gormley, K. & Ndah, A., 2024. Solent Workshop 3. Logic chains. Report produced for the NERC/ESRC-funded Sea the Value Project, May 2024. <https://pml.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Solent-Workshop-3-Report.pdf>
13. Collar, M., Contento, C., Dickie, I., Watson, S.C.L., Broszeit, S., Preston, J., Van der Schatte, A., Watson, G., Anbleyth-Evans, J., Burdon, D., Potts, T., Chan, C., Chung, P., Tinch, R., Erskine, A., Watts, A., Beaumont N. (2025). Sea the Value Marine Natural Capital Training Materials. Plymouth, UK. 14pp. https://pml.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/seathevalue_training_materials.pdf
14. Burdon, D., Potts, T., Van Der Schatte Olivier, A., Gormley, G., Anbleyth-Evans, J., Beaumont, N.J., Ndah, A., Paxton, V., Preston, J., Watson, G.J. & Watson, S.C.L., 2025. Participatory mapping to support coastal communities to 'Sea the Value' of marine restoration initiatives. Poster presentation at Coastal Futures, London, UK January 2025.
15. Burdon, D., Potts, T., Van Der Schatte Olivier, A., Gormley, G., Anbleyth-Evans, J., Beaumont, N.J., Ndah, A., Paxton, V., Preston, J., Watson, G.J. & Watson, S.C.L., submitted. Participatory mapping to support coastal communities to 'Sea the Value' of marine restoration initiatives. *Submitted to Ecosystem Services*, September 2025.
16. Gormley, K. et al. in prep. Is participatory mapping a cost-effective method to map estuarine and coastal habitats? *In preparation*.
17. Burdon, D., Potts, T., Tillin, H., Watson, S.C.L. & Anderson, L., *submitted 2025*. A Decade of the marine ecosystem service matrix approach: Review of applications, developments and future research. Submitted to *Ecosystem Services*, November 2025.

Step 5 Improving rigour around monetary values

Accurate monetary valuation of ecosystem services is necessary for inclusion in economic appraisals (e.g. cost-benefit analysis) to support robust decision-making and best make use of the competing demands on land and sea. This includes decisions on ecosystem restoration activities, and requires both accurate assessment of the environmental change, and evidence on the economic value of those changes.

The natural capital framework enables this combination of environmental and economic data in an assessment of the potential impacts of coastal restoration scenarios on regulating services in England and Scottish waters, namely carbon regulation and biodiversity (species abundance) benefits.

We utilised a natural capital approach, integrating environmental, economic and social data from across Steps 1-4. The data combined within the analytical framework outlined below, describing how changes in management actions around the coastal zone impact society (in monetary terms). This is conceptually described in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Economic valuation framework for marine and coastal restoration

This approach ensures that management interventions around the coastal environment view nature as an asset, capable of sustaining multiple benefits. It therefore discourages an approach which focuses solely on single benefits (e.g., fisheries management) at the expense of others (i.e., trade offs between different ecosystem services types or benefits), and/or the extent and condition of the natural capital asset itself.

Application of this approach in StV is illustrated in Figure 19. Based on assumed future trends in size and condition of the coastal and marine natural capital assets in the case study areas, and the delivery ecosystem services over time, annual values are calculated. Present value (i.e., the sum of future benefits) is calculated over the time period of the management actions to estimate the value of marine natural capital under different management regimes.

To estimate or assess changes in marine natural capital over time, the asset register from Step 1 is used. This shows the state (quantity and quality) of marine natural capital before hypothetical management activities begin. The asset register is extended into a “Restoration Asset Register”, developed to reflect changes under different restoration scenarios. Of particular relevance for StV is how increases in the condition (i.e., presence of species and relative abundance) and extent (i.e., hectares of new habitat created) links to economic valuation evidence (e.g., changes in human welfare from increase in biodiversity present on coastal sites, and carbon sequestration). This is discussed in the next section.

Figure 19: Conceptual approach to quantifying (in physical and monetary terms) the effect of marine and coastal restoration

Scenario development

Scenarios were developed to compare the economic value of saltmarsh, seagrass, and oyster reef restoration with the restoration costs. These were compared and assessed against a baseline scenario (i.e., counterfactual assessment of current ecosystem service provision). This approach provides a detailed understanding of how, when, and why, the monetary value of restoration changes, and helps assess key data and management actions necessary to record and monitor this change.

There are many variables necessary to model both the environmental and economic outcomes from ecosystem restoration, and the resulting changes in ecosystem services.

Site improvement scenarios were developed. These scenarios provide “central” estimates and are based on average and conservative assumptions about the quantity and quality of marine natural capital present, and how ecosystem services or changes in natural capital benefits vary over time. These combine understanding of the on-site data, users and uses from Steps 1-4 of this Report.

Baseline

For the baseline, the habitat maps and asset register with estimates of condition and quality were taken from Step 1 of the project. These metrics subsequently link to changes in regulating services (e.g., bioremediation, biodiversity) and are the basis of assessments of the value of changes in these services arising from restoration actions.

Restoration area

Potential for habitat creation and restoration in the Solent was identified using ReMeMaRe data (Environment Agency, 2023), which complement existing habitat datasets and stakeholder knowledge to highlight feasible opportunities in the Solent. These sites were assessed using a Red, Amber, Green (RAG) rating system (Table 3) to highlight the best locations for ecosystem restoration.

Table 3: Criteria used for Red-Amber-Green (RAG) rating restoration opportunities

RAG status	Definition	Examples
Red rating	Where a site is determined to be infeasible for creation/restoration of the target habitat due to long-term use and pressures.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detrimental alteration of tidal prism • Unsuitable physical conditions • High risk local issues • Overlap of existing pipeline of future projects • Existing high quality coastal habitat
Amber rating	Creation/restoration is feasible, as long as one of the following two occur: (a) existing pressures are managed in advance of the creation/restoration activities; or (b) current activities which prevent restoration or creation exist but feasibility is only possible after 15 years.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contentious local issues • Areas with developing estuarine strategies • Possible contaminated landfill/defences • Incumbent infrastructure makes project complex and possibly more expensive • Registered parkland; protected grazing marsh
Green rating	Where restoration or creation is considered possible, over the next 10-15 years.	N/A

Source: Environment Agency (2023)

In contrast to the Solent, which has rich data on biodiversity, habitat extent and condition, the Cromarty Firth has only limited environmental data available. Features mapping from Step 2 was therefore used as the baseline of the analysis (Figure 7).

In the Cromarty Firth, the managed realignment scenario in the economic modelling for carbon matches the scenario presented in the participatory mapping (130 hectares). This increases the extent of saltmarsh in the Cromarty Firth by approximately 30% but would be comprised of several small sites of managed realignment.

Restoration asset registers

Restoration of coastal and marine habitats leads to a change from extant habitats which have developed. Table 4 and Table 5: Asset register provides the baseline habitat extents and assumed condition. The scenarios are here displayed as change in habitat extent for all

habitats except oysters where a change in condition is the idea of the scenario. list the change in extent and condition of habitat, with some habitats (saltmarsh, seagrass) gaining extent and sediments and terrestrial habitats losing extent, in the Solent and Cromarty Firth. Oysters are assumed to remain within historical fishing grounds, but that their condition improves from Minimal/Low to Moderate.

The Solent

Table 4: Asset register provides the baseline habitat extents and assumed condition. The scenarios are here displayed as change in habitat extent for all habitats except oysters where a change in condition is the idea of the scenario.

Habitat type	Baseline habitat Extent (hectares)	Assumed starting condition**	Change in habitat in main improvement scenario restoration actions Extent (hectares)	Post-restoration habitat Extent (hectares)	Assumed condition post-restoration***
Saltmarsh	368	Low	+479	847	Moderate
Seagrass	279	Low	+1,213	1,492	Moderate
Native oysters*	1,151	Low	-	1,151	Minimal/Low
	-	-	142	142	Moderate
Littoral sediments	3,449	Low	(-1,213)	2,236	Low
Subtidal sediments	694	Low	(-142)	552	Low
Terrestrial habitat (grassland)	963	Minimal	(-479)	484	Minimal
Reedbeds	40	Moderate		40	Moderate

*Note that the current extent of native oysters in the Solent is limited and that this number includes historic oyster fishing sites. The actual number of native oysters present across the baseline extent, understood to be historic fishing ground, is fewer than 1 individuals per m²

** Condition assessment is based on eftec (2024) categories for species abundance and Solent Seascape Project (2025)

***Based on judgement from the project team given their knowledge of the site, habitat, species, and underlying drivers of biodiversity loss

Cromarty Firth

Table 5: Asset register provides the baseline habitat extents and assumed condition. The scenarios are here displayed as change in habitat extent for all habitats except oysters where a change in condition is the idea of the scenario.

Habitat type	Baseline habitat Extent (hectares)	Assumed starting condition*	Change in habitat in main improvement scenario restoration actions Extent (hectares)	Post-restoration habitat Extent (hectares)	Assumed condition post-restoration**
Saltmarsh	465	Minimal	130	595	Moderate
Seagrass	863	High	86	949	Moderate
Native oysters	168	Low	40	208	Low
Littoral sediments	395	Moderate	(216)	179	Moderate
Subtidal sediments	8,351	Moderate	(40)	8,311	Moderate

* Condition assessment is based on effec (2024) categories for species abundance and Solent Seascape Project (2025)

**Based on judgement from the project team given their knowledge of the site, habitat, species, and underlying drivers of biodiversity loss

Implementation

The following economic and ecological assumptions support the quantification and measurement of the ongoing benefits from marine and coastal restoration (Table 6). Sensitivity analysis is also recommended to determine the extent to which results change based on changes in the central underlying assumptions. The main sensitivities undertaken were based on adjustments to the following assumption types:

- **Economic** (discount rates, time period of assessment, SVO adjustment)
- **Environmental** (size and timing of benefits, project failure, time lag in restoration activities and benefit delivery)
- **Governance** (management of site pressures)

Table 6: Main assumptions and parameters used in the carbon regulation and biodiversity economic valuation papers

Parameter	Carbon regulation	Biodiversity
Implementation timescales	Capital expenditure is incurred immediately Operational expenditure is annual and incurred in each year of the assessment period	
Implementation cost	<u>Saltmarsh restoration:</u> Capital expenditure - £45k/ha. Operating expenditure - £50-100/ha/yr <u>Seagrass restoration:</u> Capital expenditure - £85k/ha Operating expenditure - £250/ha/yr	
Size of benefit estimate	Increase in habitat with potential to sequester carbon over restoration period	Increase in species abundance linked with a change in a given coastal habitat over the restoration period
Timing of benefits	Start to accrue two year after capital restoration works are completed Rate of carbon sequestration (CO ₂ e/hectare/year) is constant over the assessment period	Started to accrue immediately. Benefits scale uniformly over the first ten years of the restoration period then remain constant.
Annual benefit estimate	tCO ₂ e carbon regulation benefit by each marine natural capital asset in the asset register * unit value (see below)	XXX
Unit values	£250 - £450 per tonne of CO ₂ e sequestered	£11-13 per household for an improvement in species abundance
Discount rates	3.5% for years 0-30; 3% for years 31-75; 2.5% for years 76-100	
Accounting for risk	Social Value Offset (SVO)* correction factor. Applied to the present value of the carbon regulation benefit to reflect risk of reversal of carbon benefits (i.e., reactivation).	Reversal of species abundance after year 30 of the restoration scenario.

Notes: * The SVO correction factor accounts for uncertainty in whether carbon is absorbed from the atmosphere, re-suspended in the water column and/or re-absorbed in the sediment, and in the durability of the habitat to store carbon in the long term. In other words, it is a downward, conservative adjustment to reflect the possibility that benefits from carbon sequestration do not materialise over the restoration scenario;

Results

Table 7 outlines the results from the valuation of the restoration scenarios in the Solent. More details of the findings in the Cromarty Firth are outlined in the underlying valuation reports. A core finding from the research and sensitivity analysis is the

Table 7: Findings from the carbon regulation and biodiversity economic valuation papers in The Solent

Ecosystem service	Unit of measurement	Valuation approach	Unit	Central estimate	Range in values	Driver in variation
Biodiversity	Change in species abundance from restoration of marine natural capital	Stated preference survey*	£ million, PV** 60	170	20 – 1,120	Habitat match, Beneficiary households, timing of benefits
Carbon regulation –	Increased carbon regulation from marine natural capital	Marginal abatement costs		50	10 – 150	Carbon sequestration rate, timing of benefits, permanence uncertainty
Restoration cost	Cost of activities that deliver biodiversity and carbon regulation benefits	Market prices		(130)	(110 – 240)*	Capital expenditure, Management of pressures/drivers of degradation
Net position				90	(210) – 1,160	See above

Notes: *Stated preference surveys is a mechanism through which household preferences for changes in environmental goods and services can be elicited and calculated (in £ terms). For further conversation see Hanley and Spash (1995);**PV=Present Value. For further conversation see the supporting economic valuation papers.*** numbers in brackets are negative numbers e.g., the costs of marine restoration.

This research demonstrates that the natural capital approach can be combined with detailed economic assumptions and data to inform the choice of restoration activities in coastal habitats which best support the needs of local stakeholders. It is important to reflect the range of economic values, given the economic, sociological, and ecological uncertainty that underpins coastal restoration and society's preferences for it. Quantification of risk (in £ terms) can also better understand the need for different finance and funding approaches,

and the role of public and private monies in coastal restoration. This is discussed in Section 8. The methods and results were reported in the training materials (Collar, 2025), conference presentations (Beaumont and Collar, 2025; Dickie, 2026), conference poster sessions (Collar, 2025b) and a number of papers in preparation for publication through PML. Further details are provided below.

Collar, M., Contento, C., Dickie, I., Watson, S.C.L., Broszeit, S., Preston, J., Van der Schatte, A., Watson, G., Anbleyth-Evans, J., Burdon, D., Potts, T., Chan, C., Chung, P., Tinch, R., Erskine, A., Watts, A., Beaumont N. (2025). Sea the Value Marine Natural Capital Training Materials. Plymouth, UK. 14pp.

https://pml.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/seathevalue_training_materials.pdf

18. Beaumont, N. and Collar, M. Sea The Value. ReMeMaRe conference 2025.

19. Broszeit, S., Rendon O., Watson, S.C.L., Guillen-Onate, K., Tillin, H., Szostek, C.L., Van Der Schatte Olivier, A., Burdon, D., Watson, G., Dickie, I., Preston, J., Collar, M., Barham, P., Potts, T., Anbleyth-Evans, J., Tinch, R., Paxton, V., Watts, A., Chan, Y.Y., Chung, P., Lockett, J., Rodriguez-Vargas, L., White, J., Beaumont, N. (2025) Sea The Value – Marine Biodiversity Benefits for a Sustainable Society. Conference poster.

Step 6 Application of natural capital accounting

Key skills required: Marine ecologists, desk-based research, natural capital approach, economic valuation of natural environment

A natural capital approach recognises that healthy natural capital stocks are essential to the flows of benefits they provide. Projecting benefits into the future and evaluating these in present value terms is a means to understand the value of these assets. To connect the environmental and other information from previous steps to the monetary valuations in Step 5, data on changes in natural capital assets at the study sites was organised in a natural capital account structure.

Natural Capital Accounts (NCA) are a process to record natural capital “stocks”, and the flows of benefits they provide to society. Habitat and species data is a key part of the measurement of stocks on natural capital, making NCA a means to embed biodiversity into decision making

Accounting differs from one-off assessments by generating comprehensive systematic and consistent evidence of both benefits and the costs of maintaining assets, enabling repeated updates. Accounting offers comparability across space and time, bringing rigour to the presentation of data on natural capital assets, the services they provide, the benefits and hence value of those services, and the distribution of those benefits across society and into the future.

A full Natural Capital Balance Sheet consists of two parts: asset values (of the benefits natural capital produces for the business and the wider society) and liabilities (of what the business legally or voluntarily spends to maintain natural capital). The balance sheet and its supporting schedules answer five key questions:

- What natural assets are in scope? (see asset registers – Step 1)
- What benefits do they provide and to whom? (see ecosystem services and beneficiaries assessments in Steps 2 – 4)
- What are these benefits worth? (see valuations in Step 5)
- What does it cost to maintain the assets? (see Restoration costs in Step 5)
- How do costs compare to benefits over time? (see Steps 5 and 8)

This accounting structure also links environmental and economic evidence to investment and finance decisions (see Step 8) in several ways. Firstly, it measures restoration activities and expected outcomes in an asset register format, and links this to the expected costs, providing a record of what was invested in and when. Secondly, this information helps document the additionality of the changes from the investment, which is essential for the integrity of credits traded in nature markets (e.g. carbon credits), and is good practice on all aspects of investment.

Finally, NCA develops a record of project activities (in environmental terms in the asset register, and economic terms in the balance sheet) over time that helps with monitoring and verification of project activities. Through this support for additionality and monitoring, NCA helps manage and reduce project risks.

Step 7 Decision uses at different scales

Key skills required: Stakeholder analysis, desk-based research, policy knowledge

To understand the effects of marine and coastal management decisions on stakeholders of marine and coastal ecosystem services, it is important to include them in economic valuation evidence collection. This understanding will guide the design of financing mechanisms for marine restoration.

Relevant decision-making uses of marine ecosystem services economic valuation evidence include, but are not limited to:

- Local marine ecosystem restoration and management plans.
- Marine licensing and regulatory bodies.
- Financial investment models and mechanisms for ecosystem maintenance and/or restoration.
- Design of nature-markets, which can sell credits generated from marine ecosystem restoration to generate revenue to repay investments.
- Purchasers of credits from marine restoration projects in those markets.

Information about stakeholders around the case study sites was collected from participatory mapping process (Step 2 and Step 4). Multiple stakeholders in each of the Solent and the Cromarty Firth were identified. From this list, six main categories of stakeholders were determined. These included: including national governmental agencies and bodies, local authorities, conservation and environmental Non-Government Organisations (NGOs), local organisations, private companies, and academic institutions. Common stakeholders included organisations operating at a national scale like Environmental Agencies (Environment Agency: EA, Scottish Environment Protection Agency: SEPA, Nature England and Nature Scotland), and fishing management organisations (Marine Directorate in Scotland and Inshore Fisheries Conservation Authority in England) and at a local level, such as local authorities (councils and harbour authorities) water companies, boat and sailing clubs, conservation NGOs, local community organisations and conservation groups and Universities. From the results of the participatory workshops, we also determined which benefits were most important to the stakeholders. This helped us to identify how important the ecosystem services for the stakeholders, and their level of dependence. This was overlaid with understanding of how these users, and their uses, interact with habitats and species based on the pressure and risk mapping (Step 1). An example for the Cromarty Firth is provided in

Table 8.

Table 8: List of twenty stakeholders of the Cromarty Firth, their involvement in activities and reliance on ecosystem services from habitats (Colour legends below the table)

Cromarty Firth	Involvement in activities that create pressures on habitats					Reliance on ES/Benefits from habitats
Stakeholders	Invergordon Service Base	Pier	Dredging	Moorings	Wastewater discharges	
Port Of Cromarty Firth	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Blue	Light Green
Cromarty Port Authority	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Blue	Dark Blue	Blue	Light Green
Dredging companies	Dark Blue	White	Dark Blue	White	White	Light Green
Marine Directorate	Blue	Dark Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Green
Scottish Water	White	White	White	White	Dark Blue	Green
Highland Council	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Green
Offshore energy companies	Blue	Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	White
Marine Scotland	Light Blue	Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	Dark Green
Scottish Environment Agency (SEPA)	Light Blue	Light Blue	Blue	Light Blue	Blue	Dark Green
Royal Yachting Association (RYA)	Light Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	Blue	Light Blue	Light Green
Cromarty Boat Club	Light Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	Blue	Light Blue	Light Green
Residents	Light Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	Green
Tourism operators	Light Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	Green
Fishing operators	Light Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	Green
Opportunity Cromarty Firth	Light Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue	Light Green
Whyte & Mackay	White	White	White	White	White	Light Green
Academia	White	White	White	White	White	Green
Moray Firth Coastal Partnership	White	White	White	White	White	Green
Royal Society for the Protection of Birds	White	White	White	White	White	Dark Green
Moray Ocean Community	White	White	White	White	White	Dark Green
Nature Scotland	White	White	White	White	White	Dark Green
Involvement in activities that create pressures on habitats						
Highly involved: Strong influence and key responsibility, leading role in performing the activity.					Dark Blue	
Moderately involved: Moderate influence and shared responsibility, supporter role or facilitator of the activity.					Blue	
Minimally involved: Rare or passive involvement, little or no influence or responsibility.					Light Blue	
Not involved: No noticeable participation, influence, or responsibility on the activity.					White	
Reliance on benefits (Biodiversity, Bioremediation and Carbon Sequestration)						
High reliance					Dark Green	
Moderate reliance					Green	
Low reliance					Light Green	

The beneficiaries from marine ecosystem services, and the uses of the outputs from their measurement and valuation are important to understand so that they can be presented in the appropriate form to be used consistently in decision-making. One way to enhance consistency is to have a source of data and guidance for the use of marine ecosystem service values. Defra's ENCA (Enabling a Natural Capital Approach) provides such a structure. However, capacity to use ENCA in marine policy and project decision-making is not always available.

The results of this analysis (Table 9) were used to outline possible roles in financing restoration measures. Potential roles were mapped to the following categories:

Table 9: Roles that are needed in nature restoration

Role	Description
Funding	Directly finance or channel funds for restoration and environmental improvement programmes
Technical advice/supervision	Offering technical support in restoration design
Manage the funds	managing the funds for the restoration project
Regulations and permits	Give the permits for restoration
Pressures mitigation	Regulate external pressures over restoration and environmental enhancement areas
On-site restoration activities	Contribute with site selection, carry out or facilitate restoration activities on the selected sites
Community and other stakeholders' engagement	Support with local and national communities and stakeholder engagement
Monitoring	Carry out monitoring and evaluation of restoration projects

The stakeholder groups identified can carry out a range of potential functions to help implement restoration. However, it is unclear if there is a suitable organisation to manage and distribute multi-year funding for ecosystem restoration across multiple delivery partners.

The methods and results were reported in the same conference papers as Step 5, as well as a supporting paper detailing the approach to linking stakeholders with uses and investment in marine conservation evidence. Further details are provided below.

Step 8 Define and test investment options

Skills needed: Economic appraisal, financial analysis, stakeholder analysis

Information from preceding steps can inform how, and how much, finance and funding moves between different organisations and parties (a financial model) for investment in ecosystem restoration. Figure 24 shows the links from the natural capital approach (see Steps 1 and 5) and how this can inform investment design. Specifically, a critical evidence gap linking biodiversity to climate regulation and bioremediation is addressed through the creation of natural capital asset and risk registers for the two case study locations (Step 1). This evidence is built upon through participatory mapping workshops (T1.2), which input

local knowledge, and provide insights into pluralistic values and beneficiaries. It combines previously reported methods and outputs to explore opportunities for marine nature-based finance to grow. The figure below outlines these linkages between the natural science, socio-economics, and valuation evidence to support financing.

Figure 20: The linkages between natural capital assessments and investment in coastal and marine restoration

The work producing natural capital accounts on carbon regulation, nutrient bioremediation and marine biodiversity in the Solent and Cromarty Firth, and stakeholder engagement, has helped identify relevant actors required for a successful marine finance mechanism (see Step 4). Figure 21, which shows a simplified model developed in Sea The Value, with Monetary and ecosystem service flows. There are interactions between three key components:

- *Funding* into the *finance mechanism* pays for *technical assistance* and *project delivery* i.e., brings the projects into existence.
- *Projects* deliver financial returns at market rates which, through the *finance mechanism*, are sold to *purchasers*.
- The *finance mechanism* repays funders based on the nature (size, extent, timing) of the returns

Figure 21: Example financial model to support financing and funding marine and coastal restoration.

Purchasers and funders are the two means by which finance flows into the marine restoration finance mechanism (Figure 21). It is important to distinguish purchasers (buyers) from funders (including investors). Whilst both deliver financial flows into the mechanism, they take on different roles (see Table 10).

Table 10: Description of the needs of different stakeholders in financial models

Category	Purchaser <i>Firm purchasing the end product</i>	Funder	
		Investor <i>Equity, Lender, Insurer</i>	Non-Profit Investor <i>Government, Philanthropy, Development Bank, NGO Fund</i>
Capital Timing	After credit issuance or contract	Upfront (equity, insurer), during (loan)	Early-stage, often catalytic or concessional
Motivation	Compliance, ESG, CSR goals	Financial return (profit, interest, resale), risk management	Public goods, biodiversity, climate goals, enabling private capital
Expected Return	Non-financial (e.g. offset credits, ESG benefits)	Financial (dividends, interest, premiums, resale profit)	Non-financial: policy goals, proof of concept, ecosystem services
Project Involvement	Minimal	High (equity), Moderate (lender/insurer)	High – may co-design, co-fund projects
Example	Developer purchasing BNG units	Impact fund, green bond, insurance-backed credit	Grant for seagrass restoration, concessional loan from development bank, NGO revolving fund

Currently, project risk of failure and market instability are barriers to investment. This is due to high variation in observed carbon sequestration rates, challenges in monitoring and verification, and regulatory and governance uncertainty. Growth in public and private funding through government recovery funds, cornerstone projects and de-risking therefore has the potential to kickstart marine nature restoration projects but is conditional on the profitability of restoration projects once these factors are accounted for.

Natural capital assessments (see Step 5) demonstrate risks of failure and risk mitigation in economic terms. This information supports improve decision to support:

- The need for insurance/underwriting and share risk;
- How best to structure blended finance to create quantity and scale of finance in coastal and marine restoration;
- Alterations to financial products (e.g., credits) to reflect project level risks that are difficult to manage (e.g., offering relatively short 30-year carbon credits lifecycles improves certainty on attribution of environmental outcomes)

Finally, the natural capital assessment highlights that funding marine and coastal restoration beyond public grants requires a holistic natural capital approach (i.e., beyond maximisation of one ecosystem service). Allowing for the sale of ES produced on the same land as separate units (stacking) or multiple ES to be sold as one unit (bundling) offers the opportunity to scale restoration whilst spreading (sharing) risk and cost. This assessment helps quantify this opportunity and interested stakeholder (also see Step 7).

The methods and results were reported in the same conference papers as Step 5, as well as a supporting paper detailing the application of marine economic evidence in designing coastal restoration finance and funding mechanisms.

Scaling up of natural sciences data, issues and questions

Poor understanding of biophysical processes and impacts on habitats and biodiversity, combined with standardised methods and governance framework knowledge gaps, generate substantial uncertainty and reduce output confidence, particularly in marine systems. Together, these preclude effective integration into Nature-Based Solutions. These knowledge gaps stifle market-based investment centred on conserving and restoring temperate coastal habitats. To navigate this complex, rapidly evolving area, researchers from six continents engaged in a Priority Setting Exercise to generate 25 questions that, if answered within 10 years, will increase robustness, scalability and applicability of establishing market-based Instruments for carbon and nutrient in the marine environment across regions and ecosystems. The questions identified gaps which were the cheapest to answer and quickest to complete whilst having the most effectiveness in improving how marine market-based Instruments for nutrients and carbon. These focused on developing appropriate and effective methods and standards to facilitate. They also highlighted governance mechanisms and possible trading schemes as cost effective and important gaps to filled, whilst still having considerable geographic and policy relevance. Answering the questions proposed in the 25 research questions outlined here will greatly improve our understanding of ecosystem services. These answers will generate decision-grade data to strengthen green-finance opportunities, by identifying the enabling conditions for more efficient and successful approaches to address urgent climate and (nutrient) pollution crises.

Training the practitioners: Coastal Partnership Network training

The Sea the Value Project hosted a series of workshops aimed at members of the Coastal Partnerships Network (CPN) to build understanding of key concepts that the Sea the Value project aims to address. Across four workshops we discussed approaches to better

understand, protect, and restore coastal habitats, drawing on insights from our work and approach. The series provides valuable tools for participants from different backgrounds to collaborate in managing our coasts and local environments and provides a starting point for those looking to run their own workshops with local community groups and networks. It also feeds into the CPN Capacity Building Programme to create a legacy for the project learnings.

Workshop 1: Natural Capital & Understanding Value

Workshop 2: Interlinkages between Biodiversity & Natural Capital

Workshop 3: Participatory Mapping

Workshop 4: Funding Nature' Needs

Comments from attendees:

'I found it extremely interesting and useful to attend.' *'Very useful, really thought provoking'*

'Absolutely brilliant session, really interesting and I can see how this would fit in clearly with our work.'

To access the training materials please go to [Sea The Value website](#), then click on tab: *Marine Natural Capital Training Materials* to access the full resources including slides from the workshop.

20. [seathevalue training materials.pdf](#)

21. [Link to Youtube recording of training sessions: Sea The Value: Supporting nature recovery by advancing natural capital practices and developing essential finance mechanisms - Plymouth Marine Laboratory](#)

Confidence rating: dealing with scientific uncertainty

Recent efforts to create new solutions to sustainability, conservation and restoration of ecosystems include market-based approaches. For example, trading schemes for carbon, nutrients and biodiversity can be incentives to conserve or restore natural habitats that provide high levels of nutrient and carbon sequestration and storage or high biodiversity levels.

For these to work and to be accepted by potential buyers and investors, the data must be reliable. The higher the uncertainty around carbon sequestration and storage (CSS), bioremediation of nutrients (BN) and biodiversity, the less valuable are the units that can be sold on these markets because they need to include “uncertainty buffers”.

Within SeaTheValue, we extensively discussed uncertainty in data and created three levels of confidence for the natural sciences data (Table 11).

Table 11: Example confidence levels for natural sciences data. This table was the result of discussions within the SeaTheValue team.

Data/Information type and source	High	Medium	Low
Field data	Following international standards where they exist, methods based on scientific consensus, experimental design, using a control, contextual data collected, number of replicates at least 5	experimental or new approach, replicate number 3-4	Statistical significance is missing, collected in compromised conditions, no replication or 2 replicates
Quality control	NMBAQ assessment of quality of macrofauna identification	Identification carried out between 2 experts (define expert)	Identification carried out by an inexperienced taxonomist with little guidance
Data taken from published peer reviewed material	Most likely to be supported by extensive published material (both peer reviewed and grey literature). High level of agreement among sources and/or united scientific support.	There may be some published material, although some may be from grey literature. Some disagreement among sources.	Published material may not exist or may be limited/inconsistent.
Grey literature	NA	Data collected for regulatory framework for example the Water Framework Directive	Student thesis unpublished
Expert opinion	If it is intuitive and unchallenged by other scientists, united expert opinion can also carry high confidence. This may also be supported by local observations and information from other regions.	There may also be some observations from the study team.	Expert opinion may be the only evidence available. There may be disagreement among sources or expert opinion is particular to an individual expert rather than widely held.

Quality and condition

The terms 'condition' and 'quality' are often used interchangeably in natural capital discussions and evaluations. Quality refers to the underlying condition of natural capital assets and their ability to maintain flows of services (Committee, 2014). Condition is defined by JNCC as "a measure of the habitat against its ecological optimum state. Condition is a way of measuring variation in the quality of patches of the same habitat type." (Agency, 2023). The definitions imply a hierarchy of terms and 'condition' rather than 'quality' is the default term in natural capital assessments by the DEFRA marine Natural Capital Ecosystem Assessment Programme (mNCEA 2022-2025).

Condition is often linked to past and present management, and land use (DEFRA, 2024). A baseline, or reference condition provides a context against which changes can be assessed.

Condition accounts are used by The United Nations (UN) System of Environmental-Economic Accounting (SEEA) and the Principles of UK natural capital accounting. The ecosystem condition account measures the overall quality of an ecosystem asset and captures, in a set of key indicators, the state or functioning of the ecosystem in relation to both its naturalness and its potential to supply ecosystem services.

There is a wide range of condition indicators which are used to demonstrate the ability of habitats/ecosystems (natural capital assets) to sustainably provide benefits now and into the future. Condition indicators can be combined with data on extent (quantity) and spatial arrangement (location) to create a good understanding of the state of natural capital assets.

Measuring Condition using indicators

Here we define good condition as the state of the asset that enables high provision of the ecosystem service being assessed. It has to be measured in many different ways, as it varies depending on the ecosystem and the service under consideration.

In the two case studies, we infer condition of habitats in two ways. Firstly, the Water Framework Directive (WFD) has a comprehensive set of condition-based indicators which are ground-truthed and based on a five-point Likert scale that are updated every one to five years. The indicators are based on regular biodiversity monitoring assessments (which also include extent estimates). The advantage of this method is that it can be applied in areas with minimal field data as a proxy for condition (i.e. the Cromarty Firth). WFD assessment data have been collected for all main habitats in the Solent and Cromarty Firth including saltmarsh, seagrass, mudflats and oysters.

Secondly, in the Solent, we measured condition directly in the field using established indicators. Many of these, such as plant shoot density can be cross-correlated with standard monitoring-based assessments such as outlined in the first approach.

Example indicators by habitat

- Saltmarsh: Species diversity of plants
- Seagrass: Percentage coverage, Shoot density
- Mudflat: Macrofauna diversity
- Oysters: Habitat extent & density of *Ostrea edulis* (abundance: individual oysters m²), size class frequency, epifauna

Other informative variables

- Sediment analysis including

- Particle size analysis
- Total organic carbon
- Ammoniacal nitrogen as NH₃ and NH₄ (from porewater)
- Macrofauna

Further information

22. Environment Agency natural capital condition indicator mapping
<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/environment-agency-natural-capital-condition-indicator-mapping>
23. Watson et al. (2022): Inclusion of condition
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0048969722031230#s0085>
24. [Natural Capital Committee Terminology 2019](#)

Glossary

To facilitate trans- and interdisciplinary working, this glossary was created by members of the Sea The Value team.

Terminology	Description
Appraisal	Evaluation, often in the form of cost-benefit analyses, that assess different options or courses of action based on their respective benefits and costs.
Asset register	A natural capital asset register is an inventory of the natural assets in an area and constitutes the first step when completing a natural capital assessment. This is often the basis for the extent and condition accounts.
Asset-Service Matrix	An asset-service matrix demonstrates the links between natural assets, including habitats and species, and the ecosystem services that they provide.
Assimilation in biogenic material (or sequestration)	A process that sequesters (takes up) nutrients and other wastes (e.g., metals and plastics) in a habitat or organisms' biomass or other form of biogenic material (e.g., bivalve shells) in such a way that they are not biologically available and do not exhibit toxicity. Assimilation/sequestration may be reversible if conditions are altered, with the nutrients or wastes returned to harmful forms (Watson et al., 2016). Extraction of these nutrients or wastes can also occur via harvesting or removal of the organisms (e.g., bivalves, seaweeds or macroalgae) – thereby returning nutrients or wastes back to land.
Bioremediation	The removal of waste products from a given environment by ecosystem processes that act to reduce concentrations of wastes by the mechanisms of cycling/detoxification, sequestration/storage and export
Burial in sediments (or long- term storage)	The "permanent" burial of nitrogen, phosphorus and other wastes containing organic compounds (e.g., persistent organic pollutants) is a sink for nutrients and wastes in the marine environment. It is important to recognize that nutrients and wastes stored in sediments may not be permanent and may be released if the habitat is disturbed by human pressures (e.g., sediment abrasion from fisheries trawling) or if the habitat extent or condition is eroded. The length of time needed for storage to be considered permanent is subject to current scientific debate.
Climate regulation	Climate regulation is an ecosystem service that through processes related to atmospheric chemical composition, regulates the greenhouse effect, the ozone layer, precipitation, air quality, and moderation of temperature and weather patterns (including cloud formation), at both global and local scales. In this study we considered the contribution of coastal habitats to this ecosystem service, but other habitats and species such as forests and grasslands also contribute to it.
Condition (quality)	Quality refers to the underlying condition of natural capital assets and their ability to maintain flows of services.
Credits (carbon)	A carbon credit is a tradable unit representing one metric ton of carbon dioxide (CO ₂), or an equivalent amount of another greenhouse gas, avoided or removed from Earth's atmosphere.
Eutrophication	Eutrophication is a process of natural or man-made enrichment with inorganic nutrient elements (e.g. nitrogen and phosphorus) beyond the maximum critical level of the self-regulatory capacity of a given system for a balanced flow and cycling of nutrients.
Exchange Value	The value of an ecosystem service or environmental resource derived from direct market transactions, reflecting the price paid between buyers and sellers.
Extent (quantity)	Quantity refers to the extent, volume or amount of an asset, benefit or a good. In Sea the Value we used habitat extent as a proxy of quantity.

Terminology	Description
Natural capital accounts (NCA)	NCA's are a series of interconnected accounts that provide a structured set of information relating to the stocks of natural capital and flows of services supplied by them. They form part of the environmental satellite accounts. The UK's NCA's are comprised of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1) extent accounts, measuring the area of each habitat 2) condition accounts, tracking the ecological health of those habitats 3) physical accounts, presenting the annual service flow 4) monetary accounts, assigning a monetary valuation to selected services on an annual basis and recording an overall valuation of the natural asset's ability to generate future flows of services
Natural Capital Assets	A natural capital asset is a distinctive component or grouping of natural capital components, including soils, freshwater and species. Natural capital assets provide ecosystem services (flows) such as carbon sequestration and storage and water purification, which support the production of goods and services, and generate benefits.
Natural Capital Stocks	This is defined as the extent and condition of a natural resource. For example, the total number of cod that can be harvested would be a measure of extent; and a measure of condition could be the size of adult fish (which acts as a proxy for longevity and breeding potential)
<i>Ostrea edulis</i> beds/reefs	Native oyster (<i>Ostrea edulis</i>) beds create biogenic reefs as new native oysters start settling and growing on dead oyster shells. Good quality = High density. Density of five individuals m ⁻² is conventionally used in conservation purposes, e.g., OSPAR, to define oyster beds. Although some studies use 1 individuals m ⁻² .
Pressures-Activities Database Proxy Values	A JNCC matrix linking human activities to the pressures that they create on marine ecosystems. It also provides the evidence for the linkages in form of listed literature Indirect measures or approximations used to estimate the value of ecosystem services or environmental resources when direct market valuation is impractical or unavailable.
Replacement Values	The estimated cost of replacing or restoring an ecosystem service or environmental resource with an equivalent alternative, often used as a proxy for valuation when direct market pricing is unavailable or impractical (eg. natural bioremediation from a wetland versus the cost of building a remediation site or wetland)
Resilience	Ecological resilience is "the capacity of an ecosystem to absorb repeated disturbances or shocks and adapt to change without fundamentally switching to an alternative stable state". Resilience relates to how an ecosystem resists stressors and how it recovers from loss or degradation (resilience = resistance and recovery).
Resistance	Resistance characteristics indicate whether a receptor can absorb disturbance or stress without changing character.
Risk register	The risk register identifies natural capital assets where further degradation places the benefits we derive from them at risk. Identifying the benchmark or limit for each asset-benefit relationship is a key step in developing a risk register. The limit defines the point at which change in the asset becomes deleterious or even dangerous, that is it defines the nature and severity of the risk.
Saltmarsh	An area of coastal vegetated habitat that is exposed to tidal flooding with seawater
Seagrass bed	an intertidal or shallow subtidal marine habitat with the only marine flowering plant.
Sequestration into biomass (or assimilation)	Processes that sequester nutrients and other wastes (e.g., metals and plastics) in a habitat or organisms' biomass or other form of biogenic material

Terminology	Description
	(e.g., bivalve shells) in such a way that they are not biologically available and do not exhibit toxicity.
Spatial configuration	The location of an asset and/or its spatial patterning and fragmentation, both of which have been shown to have substantial effects on benefits. Spatial configuration is critical for wildlife and for recreational and health benefits from the environment but also influences many productive and regulatory functions provided by natural assets.
Stated Preferences	Indicated willingness to pay for a specific service or good, such as environmental amenities like biodiversity or bioremediation, often used as a measure of non-market value in valuation studies.
The Environmental Benefits from Nature Tool	The Environmental Benefits from Nature tool to enable wider benefits for people and nature from biodiversity net gain by employing a habitat-based approach to provide a common and consistent means of considering the direct impact of land use change across 18 ecosystem service services. It is targeted at developers, planners and other interested parties
Total Economic Value	The overall value of an ecosystem or environmental resource, including both tangible and intangible benefits, such as direct market transactions and non-market values like cultural or aesthetic benefits.
Unit (carbon or nitrogen) Value	One ton of CO ₂ (independently if it is traded in the market or not) Value is the importance we place on a thing, values can be ecological, economic or social.
Welfare Value	The total benefit to an individual or society from possessing or consuming a good or service, including both market and non-market values.

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